

Covariant Formulation in M^4 of a Scalar Field and Its Gauge Relations

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Abstract

A covariant formulation in M^4 is presented for a scalar field φ , represented as the divergence of a minimal 4-potential \check{Z}^μ , purely longitudinal and with identically zero antisymmetric sector. Starting from this minimal potential, the general family of 4-potentials Z^μ is constructed by means of gauge transformations involving an antisymmetric tensor $H^{\mu\nu}$ and a homogeneous scalar function. It is shown that the antisymmetric tensor $R^{\mu\nu}$ associated with Z^μ is completely determined by $H^{\mu\nu}$, and that the gauge source J_g^μ satisfies a conservation equation. Finally, under global decay conditions, the selection of the minimal gauge and the uniqueness of the corresponding 4-potential are analyzed.

Keywords: Covariant formulation, scalar field, Minkowski spacetime, minimal 4-potential, Helmholtz-type representation, gauge structure, wave equation

1. INTRODUCCION

The representation of fields in terms of potentials has long been a classical topic in field theory, particularly in connection with the Helmholtz theorem and its extensions. In its traditional form, that theorem allows a static vector field in R^3 to be decomposed into irrotational and solenoidal parts, whereas its generalizations to the time-dependent case were established later in the literature.[1-4].

Within the covariant framework on M^4 , Woodside [5] developed a relevant treatment of integral representations and uniqueness issues for four-vector and scalar fields, explicitly formulating the longitudinal gauge in connection with the latter. Aguirre and Bermúdez [6,7], in turn, developed a complete Helmholtz-type formulation in 3+1 decomposition for a scalar field, both static and dynamic, establishing the corresponding gauge transformations and differential relations.

The present work extends that formulation to the covariant language of M^4 , thereby completing the program initiated in those references. Its aim is to construct a formulation for a scalar field $\varphi(x)$ in terms of a purely longitudinal minimal 4-potential $\check{Z}^\mu(x)$, and to examine the residual gauge structure associated with the general family of 4-potentials that represent the same field. In this context, the analysis of the residual antisymmetric tensor and the induced gauge 4-source helps

clarify the organization of the formalism, as well as the conditions under which the minimal gauge can be imposed globally and lead to the uniqueness of the minimal 4-potential.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 constructs the minimal potential from the scalar field φ . Section 3 introduces the gauge transformations that generate the general family of associated potentials. Section 4 examines the residual gauge sector and studies the conditions that allow the minimal gauge to be selected globally and the uniqueness of the minimal 4-potential to be established. Finally, Appendix A presents an alternative formulation of the residual sector, whereas Appendix B shows how the general equation for the 4-potential can be obtained, under a gauge parametrization, from Lagrangian densities associated with the minimal sector

2. THE MINIMAL 4-POTENTIAL

Let us consider a classical massless scalar field $\varphi(x)$, defined on Minkowski spacetime M^4 , sufficiently regular and with appropriate decay at spacetime infinity. We begin with its four-dimensional identity written in terms of the Dirac delta on M^4 :

$$\varphi(x) = \int_{M^4} d^4x' \delta^{(4)}(x - x') \varphi(x'). \quad (1)$$

Let $G_r(x - x')$ now be a retarded Green function associated with the d'Alembert operator $\square := c^{-2}\partial_t^2 - \nabla^2$ which, under the singular normalization

$$\square G_r(x - x') = 4\pi \delta^{(4)}(x - x'), \quad (2)$$

allows the fundamental identity (1) to be written as

$$\varphi(x) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{M^4} d^4x' \square G_r(x - x') \varphi(x'). \quad (3)$$

Since the operator \square acts on the variable x , and not on the integration variable x' , it may be taken outside the integral sign under the regularity and decay assumptions already stated, so that

$$\varphi(x) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \square \int_{M^4} d^4x' G_r(x - x') \varphi(x'). \quad (4)$$

This expression suggests introducing the retarded inverse d'Alembert operator in the Green-function sense through the definition

$$\square_r^{-1} \varphi(x) := \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{M^4} d^4x' G_r(x - x') \varphi(x'). \quad (5)$$

so that, by construction,

$$\square [\square_r^{-1} \varphi(x)] = \varphi(x). \quad (6)$$

Using Eq. (5), we now define the generating scalar functional $\chi(x)$ by

$$\chi(x) := \square_r^{-1} \varphi(x), \quad (7)$$

and therefore,

$$\square \chi(x) = \varphi(x), \quad (8)$$

that is, $\chi(x)$ is a particular retarded solution of the inhomogeneous wave equation with source $\varphi(x)$.

Starting from the scalar potential $\chi(x)$, we define the contravariant 4-potential as its 4-gradient,

$$\check{Z}^\mu(x) = \partial^\mu \chi(x), \quad (9)$$

or equivalently,

$$\check{Z}^\mu(x) = \partial^\mu [\square_r^{-1} \varphi(x)] \quad (10)$$

Taking the 4-divergence of (10) and using (6), it follows that $\partial_\mu \check{Z}^\mu = \square (\square_r^{-1} \varphi) = \varphi$, and therefore,

$$\varphi(x) = \partial_\mu \check{Z}^\mu(x), \quad (11)$$

which provides the fundamental covariant representation of the scalar field in terms of $\check{Z}^\mu(x)$, hereafter called the minimal 4-potential, anticipating its role in the general structure of the formalism.

Recalling that the contravariant 4-gradient in the signature $(+, -, -, -)$ is expressed as $\partial^\mu = (c^{-1} \partial_t, -\nabla)$, and substituting into definition (9), one obtains

$$\check{Z}^\mu = (c^{-1} \partial_t \chi, -\nabla \chi). \quad (12)$$

Introducing now the minimal three-dimensional fields defined at the same spacetime point x , or equivalently at (t, \mathbf{x}) ,

$$\Omega_o(x) := c^{-1} \partial_t \chi(x), \quad \mathbf{Z}_o(x) := \nabla \chi(x), \quad (13)$$

the minimal 4-potential takes the compact form

$$\check{Z}^\mu = (\Omega_o, -\mathbf{Z}_o). \quad (14)$$

The covariant representation of the scalar field is obtained by contracting the contravariant 4-potential $\check{Z}^\mu(x)$ with the covariant 4-gradient $\partial_\mu = (c^{-1} \partial_t, \nabla)$, from which there follows

$$\partial_\mu \check{Z}^\mu = \partial_0 \check{Z}^0 + \partial_i \check{Z}^i \quad (15)$$

where summation over $i=1,2,3$ is understood. Substituting into Eq. (15) the components of $\check{Z}^\mu(x)$ given by Eq. (14), namely $\check{Z}^0(x) = \Omega_o(x)$ y $\check{Z}^i(x) = -Z_o^i(x)$, one obtains

$$\partial_\mu \check{Z}^\mu = c^{-1} \partial_t \Omega_o + \partial_i (-Z_o^i). \quad (16)$$

Now, since $\partial_i Z_o^i$ is simply the spatial divergence of \mathbf{Z}_o , the above expression may be written as

$$\partial_\mu \check{Z}^\mu = c^{-1} \partial_t \Omega_o - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{Z}_o, \quad (17)$$

from which, by virtue of the fundamental covariant relation established in Eq. (11), one obtains the explicit 3+1 form of the scalar field [6,7]:

$$\varphi = c^{-1} \partial_t \Omega_o - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{Z}_o \quad (18)$$

Returning to Eq. (11), we see that the scalar field $\varphi(x)$ is determined by the 4-divergence of the minimal potential $\check{Z}^\mu(x)$, thus fixing the scalar content of the formulation. In a covariant formalism on M^4 , however, the significance of a 4-potential does not necessarily reduce to its divergence, but may also reside in its associated antisymmetric part. This is the case in electromagnetism, where the tensor $F^{\mu\nu}(x)$ describes the physical content of the field independently of the divergence of $A^\mu(x)$. It is therefore natural to examine here the role played by the antisymmetric structure associated with $\check{Z}^\mu(x)$.

Accordingly, we define the tensor $\check{R}^{\mu\nu}(x)$ by

$$\check{R}^{\mu\nu} = \partial^\mu \check{Z}^\nu - \partial^\nu \check{Z}^\mu, \quad (19)$$

where, in view of Eq. (9)

$$\check{R}^{\mu\nu} = \partial^\mu \partial^\nu \chi - \partial^\nu \partial^\mu \chi = 0, \quad (20)$$

provided the partial derivatives commute on χ , and consequently,

$$\check{R}^{\mu\nu} = 0. \quad (21)$$

It should be noted that the property $\check{R}^{\mu\nu}(x) = 0$ implies that $\check{Z}^\mu(x)$ is a pure gauge potential in the usual sense, since its associated antisymmetric tensor vanishes identically. This vanishing, however, does not imply physical triviality here, because the 4-divergence $\partial_\mu \check{Z}^\mu(x)$ may be nonzero. Thus, the pure-gauge character of $\check{Z}^\mu(x)$ refers only to its antisymmetric part.

To make the content of property (21) explicit in the 3+1 decomposition, let us first consider the spatial components ($i, j = 1, 2, 3$). From the definition (19) and the form (14), one obtains

$$\check{R}^{ij} = \partial^i \check{Z}^j - \partial^j \check{Z}^i = \partial^i (-Z_o^j) - \partial^j (-Z_o^i), \quad (22)$$

from which it follows that

$$\check{R}^{ij} = -(\partial^i Z_o^j - \partial^j Z_o^i). \quad (23)$$

and, using the three-dimensional Levi-Civita symbol ε_{kij} , the covariant component of the curl is

$$(\nabla \times \mathbf{Z}_o)_k = \varepsilon_{kij} \partial^i Z_o^j = -\frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_{kij} \check{R}^{ij}. \quad (24)$$

On the other hand, for the mixed components,

$$\check{R}^{i0} = \partial^i \check{Z}^0 - \partial^0 \check{Z}^i, \quad (25)$$

and using $\partial^i = -\partial_i$, $\partial^0 = \partial_0 = c^{-1} \partial_t$, $\check{Z}^0 = \Omega_o$ y $\check{Z}^i = -Z_o^i$, one finds

$$\check{R}^{i0} = -\partial_i \Omega_o + c^{-1} \partial_t Z_o^i. \quad (26)$$

Thus, the covariant ‘‘minimal’’ property (21), as expressed in Eqs. (24) and (26), is equivalent in the 3+1 decomposition to the minimal differential identities [5-7]

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{Z}_o = \mathbf{0}, \quad \nabla \Omega_o - c^{-1} \partial_t \mathbf{Z}_o = \mathbf{0}, \quad (27)$$

which constitute, in the 3+1 decomposition, the characteristic differential structure of the pair of minimal potentials (Ω_o, \mathbf{Z}_o) .

We may now formulate the following

Theorem 1. *Every scalar field $\varphi(x)$, defined on M^4 under appropriate regularity and decay conditions at spacetime infinity, admits a covariant representation in terms of the 4-divergence of a contravariant field called the minimal 4-potential, provided that the latter satisfies the tensorial identity (21). This potential is determined by the generating scalar $\chi(x) = \square_r^{-1} \varphi(x)$ introduced in (7), while the 3+1 reduction of (21) leads to the differential identities (27).*

We now show that the minimal tensorial identity also leads to the inhomogeneous wave equation for the 4-potential $\check{Z}^\mu(x)$. Indeed, taking the divergence of $\check{R}^{\mu\nu}(x)$ with respect to the second index in expression (19), one obtains

$$\partial_\nu \check{R}^{\mu\nu} = \partial_\nu \partial^\mu \check{Z}^\nu - \partial_\nu \partial^\nu \check{Z}^\mu. \quad (28)$$

Since the partial derivatives commute, and taking into account representation (11), the above expression may be rearranged as

$$\square \check{Z}^\mu = \partial^\mu \varphi - \partial_\nu \check{R}^{\mu\nu}, \quad (29)$$

which corresponds to a differential equation for the minimal 4-potential $\check{Z}^\mu(x)$. But, upon taking into account the tensorial identity $\check{R}^{\mu\nu}(x) = 0$ given in (21), equation (29) reduces to a genuine inhomogeneous wave equation,

$$\square \check{Z}^\mu = S_\varphi^\mu, \quad (30)$$

where, by virtue of (10), we have defined $S_\varphi^\mu(x) := \partial^\mu \varphi(x) = \square \partial^\mu \square_r^{-1} \varphi(x)$ as the effective 4-source associated with the field $\varphi(x)$.

3. GAUGE TRANSFORMATIONS

However, at this point we should ask whether, besides the 4-potential $\check{Z}^\mu(x)$, there exist other 4-potentials associated with the scalar field $\varphi(x)$ that still satisfy equation (29) and yet are not minimal. To answer this question, we generalize in this framework the concept of 4-potential according to the following

Definition. *The field $Z^\mu(x)$ is a 4-potential associated with the scalar field $\varphi(x)$ if and only if it determines it through*

$$\varphi(x) = \partial_\mu Z^\mu(x) \quad (31)$$

and satisfies the differential equation

$$\square Z^\mu(x) = S_\varphi^\mu(x) + J_g^\mu(x), \quad (32)$$

where the function $S_\varphi^\mu(x)$, given throughout M^4 as the 4-gradient of the scalar field, constitutes the effective 4-source associated with $\varphi(x)$ and, being exact and longitudinal, satisfies $K_\varphi^{\mu\nu} \equiv \partial^\mu S_\varphi^\nu - \partial^\nu S_\varphi^\mu = 0$. In turn,

$$J_g^\mu(x) \equiv -\partial_\nu R^{\mu\nu}(x), \quad R^{\mu\nu}(x) = \partial^\mu Z^\nu(x) - \partial^\nu Z^\mu(x). \quad (33)$$

represents the gauge 4-source induced by the antisymmetric part of the general 4-potential $Z^\mu(x)$, and satisfies identically $\partial_\mu J_g^\mu(x) = 0$. Consequently, $R^{\mu\nu}(x)$ –and therefore $J_g^\mu(x)$ – may be chosen arbitrarily, in which case equation (32) represents a genuine inhomogeneous wave equation. In particular, the condition

$$R^{\mu\nu}(x) = 0 \quad (34)$$

represents the simplest choice, namely, the one that eliminates the gauge source and which we call the “minimal gauge”.

In view of the above, the family of associated 4-potentials $Z^\mu(x)$ may be obtained from the minimal potential $\check{Z}^\mu(x)$ according to the following

Theorem 2: *The representation (31) for a scalar field $\varphi(x)$ is invariant under the gauge transformation*

$$Z^\mu = \check{Z}^\mu - \partial^\mu \tilde{\omega} + \partial_\nu H^{\mu\nu}, \quad H^{\mu\nu} = -H^{\nu\mu}, \quad (35)$$

where the scalar function $\tilde{\omega}(x)$, associated with the residual longitudinal gauge, is any solution of the homogeneous wave equation $\square \tilde{\omega}(x) = 0$, whereas $H^{\mu\nu}$ is an arbitrary antisymmetric tensor.

Indeed, taking the 4-divergence of (35), the second term vanishes by hypothesis. Moreover, if one defines $G^\mu(x) \equiv \partial_\nu H^{\mu\nu}(x)$, then, since $H^{\mu\nu}(x)$ is antisymmetric, the third term satisfies

$$\partial_\mu G^\mu = \partial_\mu \partial_\nu H^{\mu\nu} = 0, \quad (36)$$

The 3+1 expressions of the transformations (35) are easily obtained if the components $H^{\mu\nu}(x)$ are parametrized in terms of a 3-vector $\tilde{Q}(t, \mathbf{x})$ y un pseudovector $\tilde{W}(t, \mathbf{x})$ as:

$$H^{0i} = -\tilde{Q}^i, \quad H^{ij} = -\varepsilon^{ijk} \tilde{W}_k, \quad (37)$$

thereby preserving the fact that $H^{\mu\nu}$ is antisymmetric and clearly separating the part associated with \tilde{Q}^i from the rotational part linked to \tilde{W}^i .

Then, considering the temporal and spatial components of (35),

$$Z^0 = \check{Z}^0 - \partial^0 \tilde{\omega} + \partial_\nu H^{0\nu} \quad (38a)$$

$$-Z^i = -\check{Z}_o^i - \partial^i \tilde{\omega} + \partial_\nu H^{i\nu} \quad (38b)$$

and using the contravariant 4-potential (14), the parametrization (37), $\partial^i = -\partial_i$, $\partial^0 = c^{-1} \partial_t$, and the identities

$$\partial_\nu H^{0\nu} = -\nabla \cdot \tilde{Q}, \quad \partial_\nu H^{i\nu} = c^{-1} \partial_t \tilde{Q}^i - (\nabla \times \tilde{W})^i, \quad (39)$$

one directly obtains the gauge transformations in 3+1 form:

$$\Omega = \Omega_o - \nabla \cdot \tilde{Q} - c^{-1} \partial_t \tilde{\omega}, \quad (40)$$

$$\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{Z}_o - \nabla \tilde{\omega} + \nabla \times \tilde{W} - c^{-1} \partial_t \tilde{Q}$$

where the gauge function $\tilde{Q}(t, \mathbf{x})$ and $\tilde{W}(t, \mathbf{x})$ are arbitrary.[3]

4. RESIDUAL GAUGE SECTOR AND UNIQUENESS

Now, the gauge freedom involved in choosing the tensor $R^{\mu\nu}(x)$ associated with $Z^\mu(x)$ is manifested through the gauge tensor $H^{\mu\nu}(x)$. Indeed, upon substituting transformation (35) into the second expression of (33), and using the property $\check{R}^{\mu\nu}(x)=0$ together with the commutativity of partial derivatives on $\tilde{\omega}(x)$, one may establish the following

Theorem 3. *Under transformation (35), the antisymmetric tensor $R^{\mu\nu}(x)$ associated with the general 4-potential $Z^\mu(x)$ receives no contribution from the homogeneous longitudinal function $\tilde{\omega}(x)$ and is completely determined by the gauge tensor $H^{\mu\nu}(x)$ in the form*

$$R^{\mu\nu} = \partial^\mu \partial_\alpha H^{\nu\alpha} - \partial^\nu \partial_\alpha H^{\mu\alpha}. \quad (41)$$

It should be noted that the covariant expression (41) acquires an immediate interpretation when its 3+1 decomposition is considered. This leads to the following

Corollary *The 3+1 decomposition of the tensor $R^{\mu\nu}(x)$ reproduces, for the general pair (\mathbf{Z}, Ω) , the differential structure of the minimal relations (27), in such a way that its spatial and mixed components,*

$$R^{ij} = -\varepsilon^{kij}(C_Z)_k, \quad R^{0i} = (V_\Omega)^i, \quad (42)$$

allow the identification of the quantities

$$\mathbf{C}_Z = \nabla \times \mathbf{Z}, \quad \mathbf{V}_\Omega = \nabla \Omega - c^{-1} \partial_t \mathbf{Z}. \quad (43)$$

Indeed, upon decomposing the general tensor $R^{\mu\nu}(x)$ according to the same scheme by which (27) was obtained from (23), the 3+1 projection of its components R^{0i} and R^{ij} leads to the differential gauge expressions (43).

Thus, $R^{\mu\nu}(x)$ constitutes the unified form in M^4 of $\mathbf{C}_Z(t, \mathbf{x})$ and $\mathbf{V}_\Omega(t, \mathbf{x})$, introduced previously in Ref. [7]. Moreover, using the parametrization (37), introducing the identities (39) into relation (41), and using the identifications (42), one obtains from the components R^{0i} and R^{ij} the explicit vector expressions of (43) in terms of the gauge functions $\tilde{Q}(t, \mathbf{x})$ and $\tilde{W}(t, \mathbf{x})$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{V}_\Omega &= -\square \tilde{Q} - \nabla \times (\nabla \times \tilde{Q} + c^{-1} \partial_t \tilde{W}), \\ \mathbf{C}_Z &= -\square \tilde{W} + \nabla \nabla \cdot \tilde{W} - c^{-1} \partial_t (\nabla \times \tilde{Q} + c^{-1} \partial_t \tilde{W}). \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

In particular, if we wish $Z^\mu(x)$ to be fixed in the minimal gauge, like $\check{Z}^\mu(x)$, then it is sufficient that $H^{\mu\nu}(x)$ and its dual $*H^{\mu\nu}(x)$ satisfy

$$\square H^{\mu\nu} = 0, \quad \partial_\nu *H^{\mu\nu} = 0. \quad (45)$$

To make the second condition in (45) explicit in terms of the 3+1 decomposition, parametrization (37) induces on the dual the relations

$$*H^{0i} = -\tilde{W}^i, \quad *H^{ij} = \varepsilon^{ijk} \tilde{Q}_k, \quad (46)$$

thereby exchanging the roles of $\tilde{Q}(t, \mathbf{x})$ and $\tilde{W}(t, \mathbf{x})$. Consequently, the equation $\partial_\nu *H^{\mu\nu}(x) = 0$ separates into a temporal component $\partial_\nu *H^{0\nu}$ and spatial components $\partial_\nu *H^{i\nu}$, which lead to

$$\nabla \cdot \tilde{W} = 0, \quad \nabla \times \tilde{Q} + c^{-1} \partial_t \tilde{W} = 0, \quad (47)$$

respectively. On the other hand, the tensorial condition $\square H^{\mu\nu}(x) = 0$ is equivalent component by component to

$$\square \tilde{\mathbf{Q}} = \mathbf{0}, \quad \square \tilde{\mathbf{W}} = \mathbf{0}. \quad (48)$$

The preceding analysis has made explicit in 3+1 the residual gauge sector, as well as the choice (34) of the minimal gauge $R^{\mu\nu}(x) = 0$, which, for general 4-potentials, reproduces the same structural form as property (21) and reduces (32) to the inhomogeneous wave equation

$$\square Z^\mu = S_\varphi^\mu. \quad (49)$$

However, before examining whether such a minimal gauge can be imposed globally in M^4 , and thus lead to a unique characterization of $\tilde{Z}^\mu(x)$ it is convenient first to make explicit the general covariant structure of the residual gauge sector. To this end, we establish the following

Proposition *The gauge 4-potential $G^\mu(x) \equiv \partial_\nu H^{\mu\nu}(x)$, induced by the tensor $H^{\mu\nu}(x)$, admits the representation*

$$G^\mu = \square_r^{-1} J_g^\mu + \partial^\mu \tilde{\omega}. \quad (50)$$

where $\tilde{\omega}(x)$ is the homogeneous gauge function associated with the longitudinal remnant, while $J_g^\mu(x)$ is the induced gauge 4-source (33). Consequently, this source satisfies the ‘‘continuity equation’’

$$\partial_\mu J_g^\mu = 0, \quad (51)$$

which may be interpreted as a conserved gauge 4-current.

Indeed, applying the retarded inverse d’Alembert operator to equations (30) and (32), and using gauge transformation (35), one obtains

$$Z^\mu - \tilde{Z}^\mu = \square_r^{-1} J_g^\mu = G^\mu - \partial^\mu \tilde{\omega}, \quad (52)$$

from which (50) follows immediately.

On the other hand, using the operational identity $\square \square_r^{-1} = 1$ (valid for any field with appropriate decay), one has

$$\partial_\mu J_g^\mu = \partial_\mu (\square \square_r^{-1} J_g^\mu), \quad (53)$$

where, upon substituting into this expression the second equality in (52), one finds

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_\mu J_g^\mu &= \partial_\mu \square (G^\mu - \partial^\mu \tilde{\omega}), \\ &= \square (\partial_\mu G^\mu - \partial_\mu \partial^\mu \tilde{\omega}) = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

by virtue of the covariant differential identity (36) and the homogeneous wave equation $\square \tilde{\omega}(x) = 0$.

This conservation property of the residual gauge 4-source becomes particularly relevant under global boundary conditions. Indeed, if the general 4-potential and the scalar field vanish sufficiently rapidly at spacetime infinity, the residual sector compatible with a nonzero conserved gauge current may be excluded. In that case, the minimal gauge (34) may be imposed globally and, by definition of the 4-source,

$$J_g^\mu \equiv -\partial_\nu R^{\mu\nu} = 0. \quad (55)$$

Thus, the exact minimal 4-potential $\check{Z}^\mu(x) = \partial^\mu \square_r^{-1} \varphi(x)$ emerges as the only admissible representative in M^4 , provided that the homogeneous longitudinal gauge function $\check{\omega}(x)$ vanishes globally..

5. CONCLUSIONS

The formulation developed here extends to the covariant framework in M^4 the 3+1 treatment previously obtained for a scalar field, and articulates in unified form the minimal structure and the residual gauge sector.

The analysis clarifies the role of the residual antisymmetric sector and of the associated gauge source. It also shows that the selection of the minimal gauge is not merely a formal simplification, but rather the criterion that, under appropriate boundary conditions, leads to the global uniqueness of the minimal 4-potential.

A possible extension of the present formalism to the case of a massive scalar field would allow the residual gauge sector to acquire a more direct dynamical role.

APPENDIX A: AN ALTERNATIVE PROPOSAL

As an alternative to the preceding Proposition, the residual gauge sector may be formulated in the following terms:

Proposal. Starting from the gauge 4-source J_g^μ , defined in (33), and from the gauge 4-potential $G^\mu(x) \equiv \partial_\nu H^{\mu\nu}(x)$, induced by the tensor $H^{\mu\nu}(x)$ and associated with the residual antisymmetric field $R^{\mu\nu}(x)$ through (41) in the form

$$R^{\mu\nu} = \partial^\mu G^\nu - \partial^\nu G^\mu, \quad (\text{A1})$$

one obtains the inhomogeneous wave equation

$$\square G^\mu = J_g^\mu, \quad (\text{A2})$$

making use of the covariant differential identity (36), $\partial_\mu G^\mu(x) = 0$. From this it follows immediately that the gauge 4-source satisfies the continuity equation

$$\partial_\mu J_g^\mu = 0. \quad (\text{A3})$$

Indeed, taking the divergence of expression (51), and commuting the operator \square with the partial derivative ∂_μ , one immediately obtains $\partial_\mu J_g^\mu(x) = \square[\partial_\mu G^\mu(x)] = 0$.

This alternative proposal summarizes in compact form the structure of the residual gauge sector directly in terms of $R^{\mu\nu}$, G^μ and J_g^μ , and recalls the covariant formulation of electromagnetism in terms of an antisymmetric tensor and an associated gauge 4-potential, a point that has not been addressed in this work.

APPENDIX B: GAUGE-PARAMETRIZED MINIMAL LAGRANGIANS

In this appendix we show that two Lagrangian densities associated with the minimal sector,

$$\mathcal{L}_o[\check{Z}] = -\frac{1}{2}(\partial_\mu \check{Z}_\nu)(\partial^\mu \check{Z}^\nu) + \frac{1}{2}(\partial_\mu \check{Z}^\mu)^2, \quad (\text{B1})$$

$$\mathcal{L}'_o[\check{Z}] = -\frac{1}{4}\check{R}_{\mu\nu}\check{R}^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}(\partial_\mu \check{Z}^\mu)^2 - S_{\varphi\mu}\check{Z}^\mu \quad (\text{B2})$$

lead directly to the general equation (32) when they are expressed, before performing the variation, through the gauge parametrization (35). The relevance of this result is that the gauge 4-source J_g^μ is not introduced as an external source added to the Lagrangian, but appears as a contribution induced by the residual gauge sector.

Let us then introduce, from (35), the notation

$$\mathcal{U}^\mu \equiv G^\mu - \partial^\mu \tilde{\omega}, \quad \check{Z}^\mu = Z^\mu - \mathcal{U}^\mu. \quad (\text{B3})$$

Moreover, using property (36) together with the homogeneous equation $\square \tilde{\omega}(x) = 0$, one has

$$\partial_\mu \mathcal{U}^\mu = 0. \quad (\text{B4})$$

We first consider the minimal Lagrangian density (B1). Substitution of (B3) gives a parametrized density of the form

$$\mathcal{L}_o = \mathcal{L}_o[Z] + \Delta \mathcal{L}_o[Z, \mathcal{U}], \quad (\text{B5})$$

where

$$\mathcal{L}_o[Z] = -\frac{1}{2}(\partial_\mu Z_\nu)(\partial^\mu Z^\nu) + \frac{1}{2}(\partial_\mu Z^\mu)^2 \quad (\text{B6})$$

and, using (B4),

$$\Delta \mathcal{L}_o[Z, \mathcal{U}] = (\partial_\mu Z_\nu)(\partial^\mu \mathcal{U}^\nu) - \frac{1}{2}(\partial_\mu \mathcal{U}_\nu)(\partial^\mu \mathcal{U}^\nu). \quad (\text{B7})$$

The variation with respect to Z_β is then sufficiently characterized by

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_o}{\partial(\partial_\alpha Z_\beta)} = -\partial^\alpha Z^\beta + (\partial_\nu Z^\nu)g^{\alpha\beta} + \partial^\alpha \mathcal{U}^\beta, \quad (\text{B8})$$

and, since \mathcal{L}_o does not depend explicitly on Z_β , the Euler-Lagrange equation reduces to

$$\partial_\alpha \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_o}{\partial(\partial_\alpha Z_\beta)} \right) = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad -\square Z^\beta + \partial^\beta (\partial_\nu Z^\nu) + \square \mathcal{U}^\beta = 0. \quad (\text{B9})$$

Using now the representation (31), together with $S_\varphi^\mu(x) := \partial^\mu \varphi(x)$ and (A2), one obtains

$$\square Z^\beta = S_\varphi^\beta + \square \mathcal{U}^\beta, \quad \square \mathcal{U}^\beta = \square G^\beta = J_g^\beta \quad (\text{B10})$$

which coincides with the general equation (32).

We next consider the Lagrangian density (B2), in which the minimal antisymmetric tensor, defined in (19), appears explicitly. Substitution of (B3) gives

$$\check{R}^{\mu\nu} = R^{\mu\nu} - T^{\mu\nu}, \quad T^{\mu\nu} := \partial^\mu \mathcal{U}^\nu - \partial^\nu \mathcal{U}^\mu, \quad (\text{B11})$$

with $R^{\mu\nu}$ defined in (33). Hence

$$\mathcal{L}'_o = \mathcal{L}'_o[Z] + \Delta \mathcal{L}'_o[Z, \mathcal{U}], \quad (\text{B12})$$

where

$$\mathcal{L}'_o[Z] = -\frac{1}{4}R_{\mu\nu}R^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}(\partial_\mu Z^\mu)^2 - S_{\varphi\mu}Z^\mu, \quad (\text{B13})$$

$$\Delta \mathcal{L}'_o[Z, \mathcal{U}] = \frac{1}{2}R_{\mu\nu}T^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{4}T_{\mu\nu}T^{\mu\nu} + S_{\varphi\mu}\mathcal{U}^\mu. \quad (\text{B14})$$

In the variational calculation with respect to Z_β , $T^{\mu\nu}$ is not varied, and $S_{\varphi\mu} \equiv (S_\varphi)_\mu$ is kept fixed as a given effective 4-source. For this variation, the required contributions are

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}'_o[Z]}{\partial(\partial_\alpha Z_\beta)} = -R^{\alpha\beta} - (\partial_\mu Z^\mu)g^{\alpha\beta}, \quad \frac{\partial \Delta \mathcal{L}'_o[Z, \mathcal{U}]}{\partial(\partial_\alpha Z_\beta)} = T^{\alpha\beta}. \quad (\text{B15})$$

Since $(\partial \mathcal{L}'_o / \partial Z_\beta) = -S_\varphi^\beta$, the Euler-Lagrange equation yields

$$\partial_\alpha \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}'_o}{\partial(\partial_\alpha Z_\beta)} \right) - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}'_o}{\partial Z_\beta} = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \partial_\alpha R^{\alpha\beta} + \partial^\beta (\partial_\mu Z^\mu) - \partial_\alpha T^{\alpha\beta} = S_\varphi^\beta. \quad (\text{B16})$$

If we now use the identities

$$\partial_\alpha R^{\alpha\beta} = \square Z^\beta - \partial^\beta (\partial_\mu Z^\mu), \quad \partial_\alpha T^{\alpha\beta} = \square \mathcal{U}^\beta - \partial^\beta (\partial_\mu \mathcal{U}^\mu), \quad (\text{B17})$$

which follow from the second equality in (29) and from (B13), respectively, together with (B4), the Euler-Lagrange equation reduces to

$$\square Z^\beta - \square \mathcal{U}^\beta = S_\varphi^\beta, \quad (\text{B18})$$

since the longitudinal terms cancel. Hence one obtains again (B10), and therefore the general equation (32).

Thus, although the densities \mathcal{L}_o and \mathcal{L}'_o are not identical as functional expressions, they lead to the same general equation (32) once the gauge parametrization (35) is introduced. This dynamical equivalence, established at the variational level through the corresponding *pull-back*, shows that the conserved gauge 4-source J_g^μ emerges from the residual gauge sector, rather than being postulated as an external source.

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